

AZANZA GARCKEANA (GORON TULA) AQUEOUS EXTRACT AFFECTS FEMALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM AND FUNCTIONS IN WISTAR RATS.

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Abstract: Azanza garckeana (*A. garckeana*) is a popular fruit tree in Nigeria, precisely in Gombe State, where it is locally called "Goron Tula" which means "Kola of Tula". Apart from being an edible fruit, several uses of this fruit have been recorded. More so, it has been associated with a lot of medicinal benefits including therapeutics for fertility issues, reduction of high blood pressure, treatment of liver problems, and as immune boosters. Hence, this study was carried out to evaluate the effects of *A. garckeana* on female reproductive system and functions. Fifteen (15) female rats weighing 180-250g were used in this study. The rats were divided into three groups (A, B and C) of 5 rats in each group. Group A was designated as the control group while groups B and C were the test groups. Group A received distilled water, while groups B and C were administered 0.3 mls and 0.6 mls of Goron Tula aqueous extract respectively via oral gavage daily. After 6 weeks, the rats were sacrificed, and the reproductive organs (uteri and ovaries) and sera obtained. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used for hormonal assays. Reproductive organs were weighed and tissue histology was determined using Haemoxylins/eosin staining technique. Vaginal smear was carried out daily to determine the estrus cycle of the rats. *A. garckeana* aqueous extract caused a significant increase in the weights of the rats in groups B and C when compared with control group. There was no significant change in the serum hormonal levels of Follicle stimulating hormone. There was an observable increase in the levels of luteinizing hormone of the high dose groups when compared with groups A and B. There was no significant change in the serum levels of estradiol of rats in the test groups when compared to control group. No observable difference was seen in the histology of the reproductive tissues across all groups. The antral follicles were significantly increased in the test groups when compared to the control. Goron Tula prolonged the estrus stage of the estrus cycle in the high dose group (group C). There was a significant increase in the number of pups of the test groups when compared

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to the control. Prolonged ingestion of Goron Tula extract may enhance female reproductive system, increase gonadotropin levels, subsequently increase folliculogenesis and consequently improve female fecundity.

INTRODUCTION

Azanza garckeana (A. garckeana) also known as Goron Tula (kola of Tula) in Hausa, belongs to the Malvaceae family. It is solely grown in the Gombe State community of Tula. It is a versatile tropical African eating fruit. It is an essential medicinal and food plant that is frequently used as a natural medicine in Northern Nigeria (Ahmed et al., 2016, 2022). A. garckeana is valuable edible indigenous fruit tree species confined to Tula in Kaltungo local government area of Gombe State. A. garckeana has been reportedly used in traditional medicine for the treatment and management of more than 20 human diseases such as infertility, sexually transmitted disease, menstrual abnormalities (Glew et al., 2005). It is also used as herbal remedy for other diseases states like cough, chest pains, infertility, menstruation abnormalities, sexually transmitted infections and hepatic impairments (Ahmed et al., 2024, Glew et al., 2005, Ahmed, 2017). Phytochemical and pharmacological screenings of the plant indicates that it possesses antihyperglycemic properties as well making it a good source of blood sugar control (Williams et al., 2019). Phytochemical analyses have revealed that A. garckeana contains various phytochemical compounds such as flavonoids, amino acids,

glycosides, saponins, sterols. Ehigiator et al., (2021) investigated the aphrodisiac properties of A. garckeana, and it was that the aqueous extract of A. garckeana caused a significant increase in the vagina width and lubrication of Oryctolagus cuniculus and significantly enhanced vaginal muscle relaxations and vaginal secretions upon sexual stimulation. Hence, this study investigated the effect of A. garckeana aqueous extracted on the female reproductive system and functions in adult female Wistar rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals

Fifteen female Wistar rats were obtained from the Animal House of Lagos State University College of Medicine (LASUCOM), Ikeja, Lagos State, Nigeria. The rats were fed with standard rat chow from Agege Livestock Feed Mills, Agege, Lagos, Nigeria and water ad libitum. The animals were kept in an environment of 12 hours' dark and 12 hours' light cycle and at room temperature. They were allowed to acclimatize for 2 weeks prior to the study. Ethics approval was obtained from Animal Research Ethics Committee of Lagos State University College of Medicine and its rules and regulations for animal experimentation were strictly adhered to.

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Preparation of Azanza garckeana (Goron Tula) aqueous extract.

Fresh fruits were properly washed with lukewarm water to remove any dirt. The seeds were then removed from the fruit. Thereafter, the fruit bulbs were boiled until all the juice has been extracted from it. After that the heat was turned off, and the extract was left to cool before collecting the juice in a container with tight lid.

Experimental design

The rats were randomly divided into 3 experimental groups. Group A was the control group while groups B and C served as the test groups. Each group consists of 5 rats. Group A received distilled water and while group B (Low dose group) received 0.3 ml of the extract. Group C (High dose group) received 0.6 ml of the aqueous extract of *A. garckeana* via oral gavage for 6 weeks. After 6 weeks of administration, the rats were anaesthetized using ketamine HCL. Blood samples collected via retroorbital method and cardiac puncture were stored in plain sample bottles for hormonal assay in -20°C until used. Uteri and ovaries removed from each rat were weighed and stored in 10% buffered formalin for Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) staining.

Serum Preparation

Blood samples collected in plain bottles were centrifuged (Surgifriend centrifuge, Model SMBO-2, England) for 20mins at 2500rpm; the serum was aliquoted and placed in a clean Eppendorf tube stored at -20°C until used.

Hormonal Assay

The reproductive hormones; Follicle stimulating hormones (FSH), Luteinizing hormones (LH), Estradiol and Progesterone concentrations were determined using enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits as outlined in the manufacturer's manual. The procedure had previously been described (Ajonuma et al. 2017a, Ajonuma et al 2017b). In brief, the serum hormone concentrations were then determined from their respective calibration curves. The microwells were formatted for each serum reference. 25ul of enzyme reagent was added to the wells. 100ul of enzyme conjugate was added. The micro wells were swirled gently for 20secs to enable mixing. The micro wells were covered to incubate for 60 minutes at room temperature. After incubation, the content of the micro wells was discarded. 350ul of wash buffer was added and washing was repeated for a minimum of five times and blotted on an adsorbent paper. 100ul of substrate solution was added to each well. The micro wells were incubated at room temperature for 20 minutes. 50ul of stop solution was added to each well and was gently mixed for 20 seconds. The solution was read within 30 minutes, and each well was read at 450nm using a reference wavelength of 630nm on a STAT Fax 4700 ELISA micro well strip reader (Stat Fax Awareness Technologies, USA).

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Haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining

This was carried out on the ovaries and uteri that were fixed in 10% buffered formalin as described Ajonuma et al. (2005) with modifications (Ajonuma et al. 2017a, Ajonuma et al 2017b). In brief, fixed tissue is transferred In this procedure, the collected organs previously stored in 10% formalin were cut in slabs of about 0.5cm thick transversely and fixed in 10% formalin for a day after which it was transferred to 70% alcohol (ethanol) to cause the transversely cut tissues to become dehydrated. The tissues were passed through 90% of alcohol and chloroform for different durations before they were eventually transferred into two changes of molten paraffin wax for 20 minutes each in an oven of 570C. Serial sections were cut using rotary microtome at 5microns. Slides were prepared from these tissues. The slides were then de-waxed and passed through absolute alcohol (2 changes); 70% alcohol and then to water for five minutes. The slides were then stained with haematoxylin and eosin. Photomicrographs of stained slides were captured using a camera attached to a microscope.

Determination of Estrus Cycles of rats

Estrus cycle was determined as earlier described by Ajonuma et al. (2018). Briefly, cotton bud

swab wetted with normal saline was carefully inserted into the vagina of the restrained rats. The swab was then gently rotated against the vaginal wall and removed. Cells obtained were transferred to a dry glass slide by rolling the swab across the slide. The slides were air dried, and fixed using methanol. It was allowed to dry and then dipped into Field stain A for 15 times and Field stains B for 8 times. The slide was then dipped into distilled water to wash off excess stain and allowed to dry. Each slide was examined under microscope to determine the estrous cycle stages. Vaginal smear of the animals was taken daily for three cycles.

Statistical Analysis

Data are presented as mean and standard error of mean (SEM). Analysis of variance was use for data assessment and differences between groups were compared using Turkey comparison test. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. Statistical analysis was carried out using Graph Pad Prism Software Version 8.01, Graph Pad Inc. San Diego, CA, USA.

RESULTS

The results of the analysis that was carried out on Azanza garckeana can be seen in the tables below;

Table 1: Physio-Chemical analysis of Azanza garckeana Aqueous Extract

Parameter	Result/characteristics
Moisture (%)	83.19
Nitrogen (%)	0.17

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Total acidity as acetic (%)	0.22
Ash	1.17
Bulk density	1.0292
Lead, ppm	Nil
Arsenic, ppm	Nil
Calcium, ppm	721.48
Iron, ppm	857.10
Ph (10% suspension)	6.12
Magnesium, ppm	262.10

Table 2: Phytochemical analysis of Azanza garckeana Aqueous Extract

Tannins	Positive
Flavonoids	Positive
Glycosides	Positive
Saponins	Negative
Alkaloids	Negative
Steroids	Positive

Effect of Azanza garckeana on the body weight in female rats

There was a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in the body weight of rats in group C that were

administered Goron Tula compared to the control (group A).

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Fig. 1: Effect of *A. garckeana* on the body weight change of female Wistar rats. $P < 0.05$, $n = 5$.

Effect of *Azanza garckeana* (Goron tula) on the relative organ weight of ovary and uterus

There was no significance difference ($P > 0.05$) in the relative ovarian weight in female Wistar rats that were administered *A. garckeana* (Group B & C) compared to the control group (Group A).

Fig. 2: Effect of *A. garckeana* on the relative ovarian weight of female Wistar rats. $P > 0.05$, $n = 5$.

Effect of *Azanza garckeana* (Goron tula) on the relative organ weight of uterus

There was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in the relative uterine weight in female Wistar rats that were administered *A. garckeana* (Group A & B) compared to the control group (Group A).

Fig. 3: Effect of *A. garckeana* on the relative uterine weight of female Wistar rats. $P > 0.05$, $n = 5$.

Effect of *Azanza garckeana* (Goron Tula) aqueous extract on Follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) of female Wistar rat

Administration of high dose of *A. garckeana* showed increase in the serum levels of FSH when compared to the control group.

Fig. 4: Effect of *A. garckeana* on Follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) in female Wistar rats. $P > 0.05$, $n = 5$.

Effect of *Azanza garckeana* (Goron Tula) aqueous extract on Luteinizing hormone (LH) of female Wistar rat

Administration of high dose of *A. garckeana* showed increase in the serum levels of LH when compared to the control group.

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Fig. 5: Effect of *A. garckeana* on Luteinizing hormone (LH) in female Wistar rats. $P > 0.05$, $n=5$.

Effect of *Azanza garckeana* (Goron Tula) aqueous extract on Estradiol levels of female Wistar rat

There was no statistically significant difference in the serum estradiol hormones of the test groups compared to the control group.

Fig. 6: Effect of *A. garckeana* on estradiol levels in female Wistar rats. $P > 0.05$, $n=5$.

Effect of *Azanza garckeana* on the antral follicle count

There was a significant difference ($P < 0.008$) in the numbers of follicle in group C when compared to the control group (group A).

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Fig. 7: Effect of *A. garckeana* on antral follicle count in female Wistar rats. $P < 0.008$, $n=5$.

Effect of the *Azanza garckeana* on the production of pups

There was a significant difference ($P < 0.04$) in the production of the number of pups among group C when compared to control group (group A).

Fig. 8: Effect of *A. garckeana* on number of pups of female Wistar rats. $P < 0.04$, $n=5$.

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Fig. 9: The effect of Azanza garckeana on the H and E-stained section of the ovary of female rats of Groups A-C

Photomicrograph showing H and E staining of the ovaries of female rats of Group A-C showing follicles at different stages of development from primordial follicles to a matured graffian follicle. Plate **A** demonstrate follicles from primordial stage to secondary stages, plate **B** shows more of matured graffian follicles and plate **C** shows the

follicle from primordial to matured graffian follicle; **A**= Control, **B**=Low dose, **C**= High dose. Magnification $\times 10$.

Fig. 10: The effect of Azanza garckeana on the H and E-stained section of the uterus of female rats of Groups A-C

Photomicrograph showing the H and E-staining of the uterus of female rat in group A-C

Plate **A** shows the normal cellular architecture of the uterus, plate **B** showing normal cellular

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architecture, with epithelia lining, lumen between the cells, and uterine gland, plate C also possess a normal cellular architecture;

A=Control, B=Low dose High dose, C=high dose,

U= uterine gland, E= epithelium, L= lumen.

Magnification×10

EFFECT OF AZANZA GARCKEANA CRUDE EXTRACT ON ESTRUS CYCLE OF FEMALE RAT

Table 3: Estrous cycle of group A

Days/Groups	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Control 1	P	E	D	M	P	E	D	M	P	P	E	D	P	E	M
Control 2	P	E	D	M	p	M	P	E	D	M	P	E	E	M	D
Control 3	E	M	E	D	M	P	D	E	M	P	E	D	M	M	P
Control 4	P	E	M	M	E	D	P	E	M	D	D	E	M	E	M
Control 5	M	D	P	E	M	P	E	E	M	P	E	D	E	M	P

P= proestrus, D= diestrus, M= metestrus, E= oestrus

The estrous cycle was normal for group A which is the control group.

Table 4: Estrous cycle of group B

Days/Groups	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Low dose 1	E	M	E	D	D	M	E	P	D	M	D	E	E	P	M
Low dose 2	P	E	D	M	D	M	M	D	P	P	D	D	E	M	E
Low dose 3	P	E	E	D	M	P	M	D	E	D	D	E	P	D	P
Low dose 4	P	E	M	D	E	P	E	D	M	D	D	P	E	M	D
Low dose 5	M	M	D	D	P	P	E	M	D	P	M	P	E	D	P

Table 5: Estrous cycle of group C

Days/Groups	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
High dose 1	P	E	D	D	E	P	M	D	E	P	M	D	E	E	M
High dose 2	E	P	M	D	D	E	P	M	D	M	E	P	M	E	E
High dose 3	P	E	E	D	M	P	E	E	D	E	E	D	D	E	E
High dose 4	P	E	D	E	D	E	P	E	E	E	E	M	E	E	E
High dose 5	P	E	E	M	E	D	E	E	D	M	E	E	M	P	E

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DISCUSSION

The result revealed the presences of these phytochemicals tannins, flavonoids, glycosides and steroids in our extract of *A. garckeana* in this study. However, other studies reported the presence of more phytochemicals like Saponins, Alkaloids etc. (Itodo et al., 2022). Interferingly, some of those studies used methanol and ethanol extracts but we used aqueous extract. The biological components and phytochemicals present in our extract have been shown to neutralize free radicals and stabilize cell membranes (Glew et al., 2005). Flavonoids are involved in natural biological response and have strong inherent ability to modify body's reaction to allergen, virus and cyanogen (Egharevba et al., 2010). It is also known to inhibit platelet aggregation and could exert a membrane stabilizing action that may protect liver from injury. Tannin has biological activities that are of benefit in the production and management of many elements owing to their anti-viral, antibacterial and anti-tumor activities (Akinwunmi and Omotayo 2016).

The present result showed that *A. garckeana* had significant effects on the growth performance of the wistar rats as shown in Fig 1. This suggests that *A. garckeana* must have contributed to this growth since its components and phytochemicals have been shown to neutralize free radicals, stabilize cell membranes and may lead to increased cell growth.

Increase in the serum levels of the Follicle stimulating (FSH) and Luteinizing hormones (LH) were observed in the female wistar rats that were administered high dose of *A. garckeana*. Though not statically significant, but this could imply that the *A. garckeana* might have an modulatory effect on the secretion of these hormones and could have enhance ovarian functions and improve reproductive health. This may have been responsible for the increased number of follicles seen in the test groups ovaries as well as leading to more ovulated oocytes. However, more studies are needed to elucidate this. Infact, high dose of *A. garckeana* also prolonged the estrus stage of the uterine cycle (Table 5) and increased the antral follicle count (AFC) of the female Wistar rats as seen in Fig. 7. An increase AFC may suggest ovulation of more oocytes which could potentially have implications for fertility. In this study, it was also observed that the administration of *A. garckeana* significantly increased the number of pups in pregnant female Wistar rats. Interestingly, this may also be the reason why the Tula community in Gombe State of Nigeria have very low rates of sub fertility reported as residents consume Goron Tula fruits regularly. The exact mechanism(s) of action involved needs to be elucidated.

In summary, *A. garckeana* helps to improve the general wellbeing, increase gonadotropin levels and AFC, subsequently leading to increased

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number of delivered pups and enhanced fecundity.

REFERENCES

Afolayan A.J. and Jimoh F.O. (2009) Nutritional Quality of Some Wild Leafy Vegetables in South Africa. *International Journal of Food Science and Nutrition*, 60: 424-431.

Ahmed, M.U., M. Ignatus, B. Yakubu, I.J. Umaru and Z.I. Muhammad et al., (2022). Alpha amylase and angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitory potential of aqueous extract of *Azanza garckeana* fruit. *J. Appl. Nat. Sci.*, 14: 283-288.

Ahmed, M.U., Umaru, I.J., Bazza, J.A., Adamu, A.A. (2024). Effect of Aqueous Fruit Extract of *Azanza garckeana* on Some Biochemical and Hematological Parameters in Wistar Rats. *Asian Science Bulletin*, 2(4), 298-303. <https://doi.org/10.3923/asb.2024.298.303>

Ahmed, R.H., El Hassan M.S. and El Hadi H.M., (2016). Potential capability of *Azanza garckeana* fruits aqueous extract on enhancement of iron absorption in Wistar albino rats. *Int. J. Adv. Res. Biol. Sci.*, 3: 245-250.

Ajonuma L.C, Bamiro A.S, Makanjuola S.L, Salami M, Carew E, Umoren G.A, Okoye

I.I, Basil C.B. (2017a), Adverse Effects of Prolonged Use of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* on Sperm and Reproductive Organs in Rats, *Journal of Health, Medicine and Nursing*, Pp. 33-43.

Ajonuma L.C, Carew E, Salami M, Bamiro A.S, Umoren G.A, Okoye I.I, Basil C.B, Makanjuola S.L. (2017b), Does Sweet *Pausinystalia Yohimbe* Affect Reproductive Hormones, Accessory Glands and Sperm in Rats?, *Journal of Medicine, Physiology and Biophysics*, Vol. 31, Issue, Pp. 46-57.

Ajonuma L.C, Bamiro S.A, Salau L, Umoren GA, Okoye II, Makanjuola SL, (2018), “*Pausinystalia yohimbe* Affects Reproductive Hormones, Estrus Cycle and Folliculogenesis in Adult Female Rats”, *Journal of Medicine Physiology and Biophysics*, Vol. 44, Issue, Pp. 1-8. Ali

Ajonuma LC, Chan L, Ng E, Chow P, Briton-Jones C, Lok I, Haines C, Chan H, (2005), “Ultrastructural characterization of whole hydrosalpinx in infertile Chinese women.”, *Cell Biology International*, Vol. 29, Issue, Pp. 785-791.

Akinwunmi O.A, Omotayo F.O. (2016). Proximate analysis and nutritive values of ten common vegetables in South-West

Fapohunda D.O, Ajuonuma U.J, Olufemi E, Bamiro S.A, Ajisegiri S.B and Ajonuma L.C. MD., PhD

(Yoruba land) Nigeria. Communications in Applied Sciences. 4(2):79-91.

Alfred M. (2017) Azanza garckeana fruit tree: Phytochemistry, pharmacology, nutritional and primary healthcare applications as herbal medicine: a review. Res J Med Plant. 11:115-23.

De Carvalho C.C, Maia J.IV, Lus O.G, and de Moraes S.R.A. (2011). Sensory Nerve Conduction in caudal nerve of rats with diabetes. Acta Cirurgica Brasileira, 20: 121-124.

Egharevba H.O. and Kunle F.O. 2010. Preliminary Phytochemical and Proximate Analysis of the leaves of *Piliostigma thonningii* (Schumach) Milne-Redhead. Ethnobotanical Leaflets 14: 570-577.

Ehigiator B.E, Okoli R.I, Ndubueze N.G, Ebong O.O. (2021). In-vivo and In-silico Investigations on Goron Tula (*Azanza garckeana* F. Hoffm), a Booster of Female Sexual Arousal and Vaginal Lubrication. J Trop Dis.

Glew RS, Vanderjagt DJ, Chuang LT, Huang YS, Millson M, Glew RH. (2005) Nutrient content of four edible wild plants from

West Africa. Plant Foods Hum Nutr.; 60:187-93.

Itodo J.I., Ayo J.O., Rekwot I.P., Aluwong T., Allam L., Ibrahim, S. (2022). Comparative evaluation of solvent extracts of *Azanza garckeana* fruit pulp on hormonal profiles, spermogram and antioxidant activities in rabbit bucks. World Rabbit Sci., 30:309-326. Mahadevan, Harold Ellis, Vishy. (2013). Clinical anatomy applied anatomy for students and junior doctors (13th ed.). Chichester, West Sussex, UK: Wiley-Blackwell.

Timothy, N. (2019). Determination of heavy metals in soil and plants along major road in Hong local government area, Adamawa state, Nigeria. Chemical Science International Journal, 1-10.

Ubwa T.S, Tyohemba L.R, Qrisstuber O.B. (2015). Proximate and mineral analysis of some wild leafy vegetables common in Benue State, Middle Belt-Nigeria International Journal of Sciences. 4(5):25-29.

Williams E. T., Timothy N, and Tugga U. A. (2019). Chemical composition and nutritional value of *Cassia occidentalis*

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Mohammed BA, Oshevire DB and Adesina
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of *Azanza garckeana* (Goron Tula) grown
in Nigeria. Clin Phytosci **6**, 2

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